

Critical assessment of the potential of forest therapy as an intervention for health and wellbeing in Scotland

Reciprocal Care for Nature and Wellbeing (JHI-C6-1)

Work Package 4

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Executive summary

- Good mental health and wellbeing has been identified by the Scottish Government as one of six public health priorities, as 1 in 4 Scots are affected by mental health problems in any one year.
- Forest therapy has been found to be an effective nature-based programme supporting mental health and wellbeing, including improvements for people suffering from stress, anxiety, depression, and poor sleep.
- Most forest therapy studies have been conducted in Asia. Participants have largely been from younger demographic groups. Although forest therapy as a practice is expanding outwith Asia, only a handful of studies explore the forest therapy-health effect relationship in these different cultural contexts and for different demographics.
- We have identified a key demographic for whom forest therapy might generate significant benefits: women 40 years and older, who may encounter challenges associated with the menopausal transition. Thus, there is also potential for our research to support women's health challenges identified in Scotland's Women's Health Plan.
- The concept and practice of green social prescribing as a health and wellbeing intervention is developing in Scotland alongside green health infrastructure, exemplified in *Our Natural Health Service*, led by NatureScot and delivered alongside Public Health and Health and Social Care services.
- This report presents insight from a critical assessment of the potential of forest therapy as a nature-based intervention, to generate deeper understanding of its component parts (programme, activity, group, nature) and how it is operationalised – the things that policymakers and health professionals may wish to consider in assessing its legitimacy as a therapeutic intervention suitable for green social prescribing.
- In our assessment, forest therapy is well designed to be integrated into clinical care on the basis that organisations and standards exist that support critical understanding of what it has to offer and ensures consistency and legitimacy in the manner of implementation.
- Alongside this assessment, we conducted a small-scale feasibility and acceptability study with women 40 years and older to investigate forest therapy as a nature-based intervention for mental health and wellbeing and for changes in relationship with and values toward nature.
- Our study responds to policy requirements for evidence-led innovation, providing insight into the feasibility of conducting research on and the acceptability of forest therapy as a nature-based intervention for health and wellbeing among a particular demographic within Scotland.
- Findings could inform development of further, larger-scale research to examine effect and significance of forest therapy, and support policy and practice initiatives to support integration of forest therapy as an option for green social prescribing.

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1. Situating forest therapy in the Scottish context

- One of the research questions posed for the Scottish Government funded^a research project titled *Reciprocal Care for Nature and Wellbeing* (JHI-C6-1) asks how publicly available green spaces might be used to address key public health priorities in Scotland, with particular attention to green prescribing.
- In consultation with the project's Steering Group and RESAS, we undertook a case study approach to investigate the potential of a particular nature-based programme - forest therapy - as a health and wellbeing intervention suitable for green social prescribing to support Scotland's public health priorities.
- We additionally explored the potential for this type of nature-based intervention to support changes in individuals' relationship to, and values toward, the natural environment. This addresses questions posed for the Scottish Government funded project titled *People and Nature* (JHI-D4-1).
- In this report, our aim is twofold. First, we critically examine the potential of forest therapy considering the Scottish context, existing empirical evidence, and the programmatic components of a forest therapy programme. Second, we relate these to green social prescribing and describe a field-study undertaken to assess the feasibility and acceptability of forest therapy as a nature-based intervention programme for a particular demographic.
- This first section sets out some of the public health challenges to which we aim to contribute. We pay particular attention to mental health and wellbeing which has been identified as one of six public health priorities by the Scottish Government.
- Also in this section, we focus in on women's health in Scotland, in particular, provision for women 40 years and older, for whom unique physical and mental health challenges relating to the menopausal transition can become significant. While research funding and public awareness of health and wellbeing issues associated with this time in women's lives is increasing, there remains a significant gap in terms of funding and understanding the array of therapeutic options that could support this demographic.
- International evidence is growing that shows the physiological and mental health and wellbeing benefits of forest therapy as a non-pharmacological intervention for conditions such as stress, anxiety, and depression. We briefly review this literature and identify key gaps – in particular, highlighting a lack of research involving women and the need for research situated in the UK and in Europe more broadly.
- The study we are undertaking seeks to further address the need to understand how and why forest therapy could contribute towards improved mental health and wellbeing in Scotland.

1.1 Key public health challenges in Scotland

- The Scottish Government identifies six public health priorities, as a foundation to support change involving the public sector, third sector, community organisations and other stakeholders [1]. These priorities include an emphasis on: communities; early years;

^a Funding is through the Scottish Government RESAS-funded Strategic Research Programme.

mental health and wellbeing; alcohol, drugs and tobacco; equality and inclusivity; and, healthy diet and physical activity.

- In this report we focus particularly on Priority 3: ‘A Scotland where we have good mental wellbeing’ [1].

1.1.1 Mental health and wellbeing

- Poor mental health is an important public health priority: 1 in 4 Scots are affected by mental health problems in any one year [2]. Policy acknowledges that good mental health and wellbeing is influenced by interaction between social, economic, environmental, physical, and individual factors throughout the life stages [2].
- Public Health Scotland are taking an approach to promote good mental wellbeing, prevent mental ill-health, and reduce inequalities – including increased focus on prevention, wider consideration of social and geographic communities to understand specific priorities, data driven/clear evidence base for programmes, and supporting local areas to put evidence into practice [3].
- Key focus and vision of the Scottish Government Mental Health and Wellbeing Strategy is on achieving parity between physical and mental health across all stages of life. By focussing on early intervention and prevention, the strategy seeks improvements in overall mental health and wellbeing in ways that support equality, access to appropriate support, equipping communities, and better use of evidence and data in policy and practice [4].
- Improvements in mental health requires an increasing share of resources to support mental health in different settings and services [5].

1.1.2 Women’s health

- In Scotland, the recent introduction of milestone policies and platforms to support mental health and wellbeing in the workplace and recognising the specific health and wellbeing challenges and needs of women, signifies the timeliness of research to support the engagement of particular communities and demographics with different forms of health and lifestyle intervention [3,6].
- Prevalence of depression and anxiety in around 10 percent of the population has resulted in greater focus on prevention, consideration of social and geographic communities, and introduction of programmes founded on the basis of evidence in mental health policy [3].
- Significantly, while anxiety in men saw a decrease in 2021, women reporting two or more symptoms of anxiety rose to a high of 18% [7].
- The need for greater prioritisation of women’s mental health and wellbeing, in addition to focusing on physical health challenges specific to women, was emphasised in the findings from a series of events gathering information about women’s lived experiences [8]. Recognition of life course and hormonal changes affecting women was associated with mental health impacts. Additionally, non-pharmaceutical support and interventions were highlighted in the report as an important opportunity and alternative to anti-depressants.
- In 2021, the first Women’s Health Plan (WHP) was published [6]. Mental health and wellbeing was not an initial priority of the WHP but the significance of women’s mental wellbeing on overall health outcomes has now been recognised, along with the guiding

ambition that prevention and treatment of mental health problems must be tackled “*with the same commitment, passion and drive as physical health problems*” [6] (p. 24).

- The launch of menopause information resources followed the WHP in October 2021 [9] and specific links and pages supporting women’s physical and mental health at different life course stages can now be found on the NHS Inform website [10], illustrating implementation of principles including a life course approach and respectful and inclusive services [6]. Menopause as a stage in the life course for women is not currently specified in the life stage model within the new Mental Health and Wellbeing Strategy [4].
- A variety of mental wellbeing tips and advice, stories and experiences, and charity links are promoted [11]. Among listed treatment options the principles of ‘mindfulness’ [12] recognise the importance of many foundational elements of forest therapy (e.g. sensory immersion, noticing, breathing, and practicing a slower pace; see Section 2) to support mental wellbeing and manage symptoms associated with stress [13,14].

1.2 International research: women’s health and forest therapy benefits

- This section considers evidence from international academic research that may be relevant to the Scottish context.

1.2.1 Women’s health research

- Recent reports have suggested that research supporting treatment of conditions prevalent in women (e.g. mental illness, anxiety disorders, headaches, migraines) is chronically underfunded relative to burden [15].
- Women 40 years or older are likely to be in the perimenopausal and menopausal time of life, with increased vulnerability to stress, depressive episodes, sleep disturbance, and anxiety [16].
- Hormonal changes are associated with vasomotor symptoms (VSM) that include hot flashes, night sweats, and somatic anxiety. VSM symptoms are associated with a woman’s vulnerability to depressive episodes, anxiety, and sleep disturbance [17]. Migraines are also a common incapacitating headache disorder associated with hormonal fluctuations associated with the menopausal transition [18].
- The menopausal transition not only lacks clarity, in terms of having a clear start and end, but women become frustrated that they are trying to function with limited treatments and solutions that might help them [19].
- In the last twenty years, many women have sought non-pharmacological interventions for managing symptoms of menopause [20]. In 2013, a US-based study found that approximately 53% of women ages 42-52 used some sort of complementary or alternative medicine to alleviate symptoms of menopause [21]. A 2012 Scottish study of women aged 45-54 reported that herbal therapies were more commonly used to treat menopause-related symptoms than prescription drugs [22].
- Increasingly, women are also turning to preventative lifestyle changes such as diet, exercise, and stress reduction/meditation [23,24]. Interestingly, a recent study responding to declining levels of physical activity among women in the menopause life stage in Scotland highlighted the significance of barriers (including a lack of support) for

women who are aware of the psychological benefits of physical activity, particularly outdoors [25].

- Forest therapy is a non-pharmacological option that could support individuals' mental health and wellbeing – including for women experiencing a range of conditions associated with the menopausal transition.
- The next section looks at the benefits of forest therapy from international studies.

1.2.2 International forest therapy research

- 'Forest therapy', 'forest bathing', and 'Shinrin-yoku' are terms used to refer to a form of nature-based activity, usually taking place in a wooded area. Shinrin-yoku emerged in the context of preventive medicine in response to a growing epidemic of depression, anxiety, and suicide in Japan's urban population in the 1980s. Other terms have emerged as interest widened and organisations began to develop programmes and training beyond the Asian context. Section 2.1 further discusses these terminologies and definitions.
- Several studies, reviews, and meta-analyses have shown forest therapy to be an effective non-pharmacological intervention supporting improved mental health [26], including for people suffering from stress, anxiety [27,28], depression [29,30], and poor sleep [31,32]. Studies have also shown that forest therapy affects physiological indicators of stress, such as salivary cortisol [33], heart rate, and heart rate variability [27,34].
- A recent review, specifically of the Asia-based practice of Shinrin-yoku, highlights improved immune response and spiritual wellbeing, along with stress reduction [13]. A study examining the efficacy of mindfulness-based interventions for migraines concluded that such therapies may be an important tool within a comprehensive treatment approach [35].
- Only a few studies have looked specifically at the benefits of forest therapy for older people or for women's health. Much of the literature to date is of younger demographics.
- Within the broader nature-health research literature, studies have found that spending at least 120 minutes (two hours) a week in nature is associated with good health and wellbeing [36].
- Here we summarise research focusing specifically on effects of forest therapy on older and or female participants:
- A study of a two-hour forest therapy programme among middle-aged and elderly adults in Taiwan found decreases in pulse rate, blood pressure, anxiety, and negative mood. Positive mood was improved, while heart rate variability was unchanged [37].
- A Japanese study of a three-day and two-night forest experience in younger women showed a decrease in urinary catecholamines and an increase in natural killer cell activity and cytolytic molecules that lasted more than seven days [38].
- Another Japanese study found that women 40 years and older experienced a decrease in pulse rate, salivary cortisol, and negative emotions, and an increase in vigour after a five-hour forest bathing session compared to measures on the previous day [39].
- In a qualitative focus group study, South Korean women aged 50-60, once comfortable in the forest space, found strength to begin healing low self-esteem, grievances, and depression [40].

- Another South Korean study describes a 6-day forest therapy retreat for menopausal women with insomnia that lowered cortisol and reduced early waking, while improving sleep efficiency and overall sleep time [31].
- Reviews of the literature illustrates a lack of significant research about the health impacts of forest therapy in Western cultures [13], though this is starting to emerge – including studies on the effectiveness of forest therapy on mood states in Italy [41], psychological benefits of forest bathing in Spain [42], and development of forest therapy practice in Germany [43]. An analysis of forest bathing impacts on wellbeing across 35 countries found that women had higher wellbeing and nature connection effects than men [44].
- In the UK context, a research study comparing mindfulness and forest bathing showed that forest bathing had equivalence with the more established wellbeing intervention of mindfulness [45]. Indeed, forest bathing was found to offer a gentler approach that encourages outward attention focus that overcomes barriers and risks relating to the practice of mindfulness (e.g. re-traumatisation) for certain vulnerable groups [46].

1.3 Scotland’s Natural Health Service

- Connections between nature and health benefits are well-established in the literature [36,47-53] and within Scotland there is an increasing emphasis on integration of nature for health [54-59].
- Development of *Our Natural Health Service* [60,61] in Scotland represents an evolution of policy and programmes founded on this connection between nature and health, starting from Green Exercise Partnerships (founded in 2007) [62].
- *Our Natural Health Service* in its current form builds on the concept of collaborative working to utilise Scotland’s natural environments and green/blue infrastructure for health and wellbeing. The initiative incorporates Public Health with Health and Social Care provision for the general population and people with defined needs (Figure 1) [60].

Figure 1: Illustration of Our Natural Health Service

NatureScot, 2025 [60]

1.3.1 Unpacking nature-based interventions (NBIs)

- Understanding the elements of interventions suitable for green social prescribing (see Section 3.1) is key for policy makers and practitioners in terms of assessing their viability as an intervention; for whom and for what outcomes, as well as to support health and wellbeing providers' communication with service users.
- Nature-based interventions (NBIs) are “activities, strategies, or programs taking place in natural settings, such as exercising in greenspaces, to improve the health and wellbeing of people by integrating the benefits of nature exposure with healthy behaviours” [63] (p.1).
- Figure 1 illustrates examples of NBIs that are incorporated into *Our Natural Health Service* – including informal activities categorised as ‘Everyday contact with nature’, and more formal programmes and interventions such as Health Walks, Green Gyms categorised as ‘Nature based health promotion initiatives’, and other therapeutic programmes for people with a defined need, categorised as ‘Nature based interventions with a defined health or social outcome’.
- Figure 2 illustrates a conceptual model of NBIs that aim to promote health and wellbeing through behaviour change [64], considering the moderators^b (e.g. attributes of individuals), mediators^c (e.g. physical activity), outcomes, and the intervention programme itself. This model overall offers a suitable framework to assess, in detail, different opportunities (e.g. Health Walks) in terms of their component parts, what is involved, and how they are implemented [64,65]. Figure 2 highlights the intervention portion, which is the focus of this report.

Figure 2: Conceptual model for investigating nature-based interventions

Modified from Irvine et al 2020 [64]

^b Moderators are things that might influence the strength and direction of a relationship. These can help answer questions such as for whom, under what circumstances, when a relationship might be present.

^c Mediators help explain the pathway or process through which two things are related.

1.3.2 Green health interventions and infrastructure in Scotland

- Four ‘Green Health Partnerships’ (GHPs) were set up in 2018 and evaluated over their first three years [54] and again at five years [60], illustrating significant value and increasing attention to programmes and interventions supporting health and wellbeing through interaction with nature.
- The four pilot areas are Lanarkshire (North and South), Dundee, North Ayrshire, and Highland – which has resulted in the implementation of a range of programmes and interventions and supporting infrastructure.
- Online portals represent a key element of green health infrastructure. These portals typically provide information and signpost users (including public and practitioners) to opportunities that might support their health and wellbeing objectives. Each of the GHP areas has an online portal (see Table 1).

Table 1: Online portals associated with Green Health Partnerships in Scotland

Online portal	GHP Area	Description
Get Outdoors Lanarkshire	North and South Lanarkshire	Signposts available opportunities and activities across the area in association with local partners (e.g. Get Walking Lanarkshire). Also includes access to resources, contact information, and a monthly nature related blog.
Dundee Green Health Partnership	Dundee	Signposts activities and resources, including videos, for the public as well as providing information and resources for health care providers.
North Ayrshire Green Health Partnership	North Ayrshire	Provides links to a range of activities, opportunities, and resources for the public and practitioners, including walking, cycling, community gardens, and conservation projects.
Think Health Think Nature	Highland	Provides links for the public (activities, resources) and practitioners (green prescriptions, community toolkits). Also provides information about NHS green estate projects (e.g. hospital gardens and greenspaces and habitat mapping project).

Note. Portals as identified to date (March 2025)

- Table 2 includes examples of programmatic interventions that support people engaging with publicly available green spaces and might also be considered as options for green social prescribing (Section 3.1).
- Early academic analysis of the GHPs found that the model worked well, that green health is a good strategic fit with public health priorities, and interventions have the potential to integrate successfully with social prescribing [66].
- Further evaluative research reported that green health prescriptions (at varying stages of implementation in Dundee, Highland, and North Ayrshire) were found to be acceptable and affordable, but issues with IT infrastructure within the referral system was identified as a barrier to implantation [60].

Table 2: Examples of green health programmatic interventions in Scotland

Programme/ intervention	GHP/Health Board Area	Description
Green Health Prescriptions (pilot)	Dundee	Referral process (forming part of wider social prescribing proposal in Tayside) for health care professionals to signpost patients to nature-based interventions – piloted in selected GP surgeries and supported by Dundee Volunteer and Voluntary Action.
Family Fresh Air Club	Dundee	Project engaging families in outdoor-based health and wellbeing activities and outings , where families from communities across Dundee are taken to different greenspaces around the city, including a short walk, healthy snack, and nature activities.
Green Gym	North Ayrshire (and other locations across the UK)	Outdoor volunteering sessions with opportunities for light to vigorous involvement, supporting physical and mental health and transforming local green spaces.
Branching Out	Across Scotland	Well-established outdoor therapeutic programme implemented by Scottish Forestry and partners across most of Scotland’s NHS health board areas. This programme is targeted at adults who use mental health services in Scotland and consists of a 12-week programme for groups of 12, participating for 3-hours per week in woodland activities, including physical, conservation, bushcraft, and environmental art.

Note. Examples are meant to be illustrative, not exhaustive

1.3.3 Forest therapy studies, training, and implementation in the UK

- Interventions and infrastructure in the previous section demonstrate the importance of principles underlying green health initiatives, that “*Scotland’s natural environment is a resource that can be used to help tackle some of our key health issues*” [61].
- These principles extend to forest therapy, indeed the role and benefits of forests in supporting mental health and wellbeing objectives are increasingly being reported in the UK context.
- A recent review of evidence, methods for, and approaches to monitoring/evaluating benefits from visits to forests in Scotland [56] cites research conducted in China, Taiwan, and Korea [67-69] demonstrating the beneficial effects of forest bathing^d for stress and anxiety. It also reports ‘strong evidence’ that visits to forests, more broadly, delivers a wide range of social, cultural, health, and wellbeing benefits.
- This review [56] identified the variety of factors that influence the extent to which these benefits from forest visits are delivered. Factors included: dose and exposure (longer visits may deliver greater benefits); environmental characteristics (more biodiverse locations may provide greater wellbeing response); and individual circumstances and characteristics (health status and income) can affect the strength of individual response. The wider cultural context may also influence the nature-health effect.
- Other research in Scotland includes evaluation of programmes promoting general recreational use of woodlands and green space around cities in the central belt for health and wellbeing benefits, particularly focusing on minorities and vulnerable groups [70],

^d See Section 2.1 for a discussion of terminology, including forest bathing which is the phrase used in the cited report [56].

and a recent report exploring barriers to accessing woodlands with recommendations for Scotland's forestry agency^e to build capacity within communities to support engagement and promote health and wellbeing objectives [71].

- Much of the forest therapy-related research carried out in the UK (including those described previously) has involved Forest Research^f. Other organisations, including the UK-based Forest Bathing Institute, are also pursuing scientific research to provide clinical evidence towards integration of forest bathing to green social prescribing in the UK [72].
- Public sector engagement with the concept and practice of forest bathing appears to be more advanced in England than in Scotland at present, including provision of resources (e.g. forest bathing activity sheets [73]) and guided opportunities within the English forestry estate [74], but capacity building in Scotland is underway, including training of fifteen forest bathing guides across Scotland in 2021 – supported by Scottish Forestry, and evaluated by Forest Research [75]. In addition to community health and wellbeing objectives, this Scotland-based project also sought to demonstrate the significance of nature connections through forest bathing with pro-environmental behaviours among participants.
- Forestry and Land Scotland have also posted a blog suggesting their top 3 spots for forest bathing in Scotland, which are Cardrona (Tweed Valley Forest Park), Faskally (Tay Forest Park), and Glentool (Galloway Forest Park), and link to more information [76].

^e Scottish Forestry – formerly Forestry Commission Scotland (FCS).

^f Great Britain's principal organisation for forestry and tree-related research.

2. What is forest therapy? A critical assessment

- In very simple terms, forest therapy can be described as a relaxing and mindful guided walk in nature, covering a short distance at a slow pace, and typically lasting around two hours. Guides are trained and certified (see Table 3, p. 17). Walks are typically done as a group although the guided activities are undertaken individually, with opportunities to share with the group interspersed.
- This section considers the concept of ‘forest therapy’ in terms of what it is, what it is called, its component parts, and how it is operationalised – the things that policy makers and health professionals may wish consider in assessing its legitimacy as a therapeutic intervention suitable for green social prescribing, which is discussed in Section 3.

2.1 Terminology and definition

- ‘Forest bathing’ is the literal translation of ‘Shinrin-yoku’ from its native Japanese into English and has been defined as “*making contact with and taking in the atmosphere of the forest*” [77] (p. 18). ‘Forest therapy’ is the term selected by the Association of Forest and Nature Therapy, one of the first non-Asian based organisations to formally offer this practice in the Western world.
- The terms are often used interchangeably, and while there has been no agreed definition for forest therapy/bathing, some organisations, such as the Forest Therapy Hub, suggest a distinction between the two based on the intended purpose (e.g. stress reduction, deeper levels of healing) and necessary extent of training involved for a forest bathing guide and forest therapy practitioner [78] (see Table 3, p. 17). The Association of Nature and Forest Therapy (ANFT) also clearly define their use of terminology, whereby their practice of ‘forest therapy’ is based on the motto ‘*The Forest is the Therapist, the Guide opens the Doors*’ – placing particular emphasis on the role of the environment and that of the person facilitating the forest therapy experience [79].
- Section 2.2.1 and Table 3 provide more information on how different organisations are using and applying the different terms through their training provision.
- From a conceptual perspective, studies across the international literature use the terms in comparable ways. Figure 3 illustrates key features that characterise the activity pursued, the environment in which it is pursued, and desired effects from participation; insights are drawn from the literature [13,26,29,31,40-43,45,46,50,67,68,80,81].
- Based on the degree of commonality across the ways that these terms are used internationally, we can say that there is a category of activities that consist of slow sensory immersion in forest environments in ways that promotes engagement with the environment and can generate relaxation and other psychological and physiological benefits.
- Here we have selected to use the term ‘forest therapy’ for two reasons. First, it lends a degree of consistency to the report. More importantly, we use it to align our critical assessment of this activity as a nature-based intervention for green social prescribing with insight emerging from practitioners as to its potential effect. In selecting this terminology, we recognise that wording carries meaning. Connotations and issues associated with the words ‘forest’, ‘therapy’, and ‘bathing’ may differ across cultures and

socio-demographic groups. This in turn may impact an individual's perception of the concept and influence their interactions as a result.

- It is not our purpose here to designate new terminology, but the importance of labelling is recognised in the context of implementation. The concept of '[Health Walks](#)' developed by Paths for All and implemented across the country is an example of terminology associated with an activity and standard protocol that is relevant here.

Figure 3: Illustration of forest therapy features, including location, activity and desired effect

Developed by authors drawn from literature

2.2 Critical assessment of forest therapy as a nature-based intervention (NBI)

- In Section 1.3.1 we introduced a conceptual model [64,65] (Figure 2) for unpacking and better understanding the components that comprise nature-based interventions (NBIs) that seek to facilitate getting people outdoors for health and wellbeing benefits from contact with nature. That model also illustrates the role of moderators, mediators, and resulting outcomes.
- In this report we are focusing on forest therapy as an intervention thus we utilise the first segment of the model to critically assess programme, activity, group, and nature.

2.2.1 Programme

- The programme itself is one of four key components that characterise NBIs and underpin their legitimacy, including programme fidelity and programme personnel (Figure 4 – drawn from Figure 2).
- Programme fidelity relates to the clarity and consistency of the approach and is crucial to a health care practitioners' engagement with that programme and inclination towards recommendation or prescription.
- Association with a recognised organisation and/or training provider promoting standards and protocols is important in this regard.

- The Association of Nature and Forest Therapy (ANFT) is perhaps the most established forest therapy programme provider currently available to forest therapy practitioners in Scotland (i.e. individuals or organisation on the ground guiding forest therapy sessions with members of the public).
- ANFT was founded in 2012, developing a ‘standard sequence’ framework for forest therapy that has been taught and adopted by trained guides in 70 countries around the world, including Scotland.
- Other organisations include:
 - The Forest Bathing Institute – a UK-based therapy and training provider, which offers courses accredited by the Complementary Medical Association (CMA) and has run courses for “*the public, government, NHS, mental health charities, corporate groups and media*” [82].
 - Nádúr – a team of nature and mental health experts based in Ireland offering Continued Professional Development (CPD) accredited training for guides, including online, nature immersion and mentored practice; Nádúr have worked with organisations including Scottish Forestry – training fifteen guides in 2021 and supporting provision of forest therapy across the country [75].
 - Nature & Therapy – another UK-based forest bathing practitioner and training provider offering courses accredited by CPD and CMA.
 - Forest Therapy Hub (FTHub) – an internationally-based network of providers offering a variety of training options, who are currently involved in a *Horizon Europe*-funded project investigating nature-based solutions (NBS) and nature-based therapies for health and wellbeing [83].
 - Centre of Excellence – a learning platform, which offers Shinrin-yoku/forest bathing diploma courses online.
- Table 3 provides details on these national and international training providers for forest therapy practitioners, indicating the different breadth and depths of training provided, including directed learning (e.g. online study, course attendance, shadowing qualified practitioners) and additional training requirements (e.g. First Aid).
- Table 3 also indicates course costs and requirements for practitioners to meet a certain level of understanding (e.g. exams, assignments) and standard of practice (e.g. on-the-ground immersion courses) to become qualified and associated with the provider’s and other relevant accreditation.

Figure 4: Programme in the context of NBIs

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Table 3: Comparison of forest therapy programmes and training opportunities

Organisation/ Country	Terminology	Training <i>Length, mode, content, etc.</i>	Cost	Accreditation
ANFT Based in USA	Forest Therapy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 6 months remote/online training + 4-day immersion course, including: - 14 modules (120 lessons); live calls with trainers and cohort; small group discussions; 30 short trainer videos; 40+ assignments/self-exploration activities; 20+ nature connection activities; access to research papers and studies; remote forest therapy walks guided by trainers; guide own walks and debrief. - Requirement for Wilderness First Aid certification to become certified as Forest Therapy guide. - Course content includes learning on ANFT Standard Sequence, nature connection, trail awareness and safety, knowing your bioregion, facilitation skills, expressive arts, competency standards, etc. 	\$3,845 (£2968) + First Aid	ANFT Certified Forest Therapy Guide
Forest Bathing Institute Based in UK	Forest Bathing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 8-12 months remote learning + 4-day intensive in-person training, including: - 2 modules; online learning calls, case studies and exams (practical sessions, practical assessment and theory exam); group training calls; training manual; prepares guides to high standard capable of integrating with NHS, social prescribing, and government vulnerable person programmes. - Course content includes learning on meditation and mindfulness and forest therapy theory, science and history, how to run sessions, etc. 	£3,300	The Forest Bathing Institute Certified Guide CMA Accredited
Nádúr Based in Ireland	Forest Bathing Integrative Forest Therapy	<p>Forest Bathing (FB)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 2-week intensive online training + 3 months mentored practice. - Option for 3 day in-person nature immersive training. - Requirement for outdoor first aid training. - Course content includes learning on health and wellbeing, Nádúr process model, forest medicine and site selection, sensory awareness, environmental ethics, safety and risk management, etc. <p>Integrative Forest Therapy (IFT)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 6-month blended online training with 4-weeks of intensive training and 5 months of mentored practice. - Additional requirement for mental health first aid and outdoor first aid training. - Option for 3-day nature immersion training. - Course content includes learning on health and wellbeing, mental health literacy, nature-based needs assessment, design, delivery and evaluation of IFT programmes, working with specific groups across a life stage model, etc. 	<p>FB: €1,000-€1,500 (£836-£1,255) based on country (high- low income)</p> <p>IFT: €1,900- €2,300 (£1589-£1,924) based on country (low- high income)</p>	<p>Nádúr and MIND Hillingdon UK Forest Bathing Guide</p> <p>Nádúr and MIND Hillingdon UK Integrative Forest Therapy Practitioner CPD Accredited</p>

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<p>Nature and Therapy Based in UK</p>	<p>Forest Bathing</p>	<p>3 stage training/levels:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Level 1: Nature and Therapy Trainee certification (3-day in-person, learning to lead small scale local walks with support and supervision) - Level 2: Nature and Therapy, CPD and CMA Practitioner Certification (1-year, self-directed learning, regular supervision and mentoring, peer group meetings and tutorials, assessment by portfolio) - Level 3: Nature and Therapy, CPD and CMA International Forest Therapy Diploma (3-day in person residential, covering nature-based therapeutic aspects in more depth and detail) - Course content includes learning on science and history behind Shinrin-yoku, practical tools, key forest bathing concepts, training manual/practical resources and templates, etc. 	<p>£1,240-£1,550 (based on level)</p>	<p>Nature and Therapy Guide/ Practitioner</p> <p>CPD Accredited</p> <p>CMA Accredited</p> <p>International Society for Forest Therapy (ISFT)</p>
<p>Forest Therapy Hub (FTHub) No country-based HQ</p>	<p>Forest Bathing Forest Therapy</p>	<p>Forest Bathing Guide (FBG)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 12-week (96 hours), 10 modules <p>Forest Therapy Practitioner (FTP)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 24 weeks (220 hours), 14 modules - Online courses, live online classes, group mentoring sessions, live online walks, pre-recorded training videos, self-guided practical exercises, downloadable materials. - Additional 3-day immersion training available. - Course content includes learning on principles of health and planetary health, design and guiding nature experiences, sequences, nature-based wellbeing, social prescribing and green prescription, theory and scientific research, expressive arts, mental health first aid, etc. - Additional FTP modules include: designing FT interventions, nature-based intervention model, group dynamics – and link to clinical, social and holistic applications, etc. - Additional requirement for first aid training. <p>Advanced FTP training also available</p>	<p>FBG: €1,460 (£1,221)</p> <p>FTP: €2,100 (£1,756)</p> <p>Additional immersion training: €290-€450 (£243-£376) based on location</p>	<p>FTHub certified Forest Bathing Guide</p> <p>FTHub Certified Forest Therapy Practitioner</p>
<p>Centre of Excellence Online learning platform</p>	<p>Forest Bathing</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Online course, 10 modules with assessment, study group access. - Course content includes learning on origins and principles of Shinrin-yoku, how to practice forest bathing effectively, mental, physical and emotional wellbeing benefits, mindful walking, sensory engagement, community engagement skills, etc. 	<p>£127</p>	<p>Centre of Excellence Shinrin-yoku – Forest Bathing Diploma</p> <p>Quality Licence Scheme</p>

Note. Monetary costs and currency conversions as of March 2025

- Programme personnel is the second significant programme delivery effect, which relates to the person(s) responsible for delivering the forest therapy experience. These are the qualified local practitioners trained to ensure programme fidelity and efficacy.
- Table 4 identifies some existing forest therapy practitioners and services offered in locations across Scotland. These practitioners illustrate examples and are not an exhaustive list.
- Training credentials and association with organisations such as those in Table 3 elucidate the extent of practitioners’ knowledge and to an extent their experience with implementation.
- While organisations implement a range of protocols, ANFT emphasise the distinction between forest therapy guides and professional therapists, whereby the guide’s role is to facilitate participants in the environment, not to provide therapy or intellectual understanding [84].
- Few studies discuss role and impact of the forest therapy guide in detail, but one study highlights the guide’s role in “*creating a space of trust and safety to facilitate sensory connection to nature and sharing of experience*” [85] (p. 298), also emphasising the role they play in participants’ experience, including “*embodiment, nature connectedness, and social connectedness*” [85] (p. 298).
- Differences between guided and self-guided experiences are also discussed in the literature, whereby guided walks are reported to be more effective in supporting positive emotional change and promoting social bonds [86].
- Positive benefits also result from self-guided forest therapy experiences [86], which provides support for ongoing benefits resulting from forest therapy when individuals implement lessons learned following a protocolised experience.

Table 4: Forest therapy practitioner examples in Scotland

Practitioner	Location	Description	Certified
Highland Quietlife	Grantown on Spey	Offers nature and forest therapy, including daytime and sunrise sessions, group and private sessions, and free monthly group session at Grantown on Spey Medical Centre Health Woods.	ANFT
An Darach Forest Therapy	Strontian	Offers guided and supported activities to increase connection with nature, including public, bespoke, and corporate events, and other resources supporting self-guided activity.	FTHub
Woodlands Breathing	West Lothian	Offers online and in-person experiences, including tailor-made events.	ANFT

Note. Examples are meant to be illustrative, not exhaustive

2.2.2 Activity

- Implementation of the activity of forest therapy, including how, how long, and how often is the second component characterising NBIs that can be assessed (Figure 5 – drawn from Figure 2).
- In the context of forest therapy, the activity can often be identified as a key element of the programme (Section 2.2.1) as organisations provide specific guidance for practitioners on implementation.
- For example, in the case of forest therapy undertaken by guides trained by ANFT, a prescribed framework known as the ‘standard sequence’ is implemented [87,88], which includes:

- A series of guided activities connecting the participant with the present moment and place.
- A series of ‘invitations’ offered by the guide, which are provided to facilitate participants to take in solitude and based on “*the intention to slow down and notice*” [89]. Between each invitation participants come back together as a group and, if they wish, briefly share their experiences.
- Sharing of tea made with locally foraged ingredients.
- Forest therapy walks are typically 2-3 hours long, cover a short distance (between 1-3km) and are characterised by a slow pace; they are about being in nature, not getting to a destination; and they are intentional in engaging all senses.
- These walks are not an intense or ‘adventurous’ form of physical activity, but could be characterised as relaxing, mindful, and accessible for individuals of all abilities – bearing in mind the risks associated with being outdoors in a natural environment (e.g. tripping).

Figure 5: Activity in the context of NBIs

2.2.3 Group

- The group is the third component characterising NBIs, including the social relatedness and features of the group during forest therapy experiences, and consideration for other aspects of interaction between participants (see Figure 6 – drawn from Figure 2).
- Key elements of interest here relate to group size, composition (e.g. age, gender), whether group members have prior knowledge of others (and how, e.g. family, friend); among other things, these can impact an individuals’ feeling of emotional safety within the group.
- Providing forest therapy as a group-based activity also impacts on participants sense of physical safety in nature.
- While social interaction is not the primary purpose of forest therapy, there are facilitated opportunities for group members to share their experiences (should they want to), which has been found to be valuable [86].
- Interaction between forest therapy groups and other site users (e.g. walkers, cyclists) has been identified as having a significant impact on experience, through loss of tranquillity, solitude, and privacy [90].

Figure 6: Group in the context of NBIs

2.2.4 Nature

- The fourth identified component that characterises NBIs is the nature in which they are situated (Figure 7 – drawn from Figure 2). This includes considerations of:
 - The type of environmental setting (e.g. park, woodland, coastal)
 - The location of the setting (e.g. rural, urban)
 - The environmental and ecological quality of the setting (e.g. types of trees, biodiversity, altitude)
 - Characteristics that could influence user experience such as safety (e.g. path composition), aesthetics (e.g. views, anthropogenic impact)
- Given the centrality of the setting to a forest therapy programme, we undertook a rapid assessment of peer-reviewed literature (empirical, reviews) to understand the extent to which this dimension was being considered.
- We searched Web of Science and Pub Med using the following strategy:
 - Geographic focus:
 - UK, Europe, North America due to similarities in biome (temperate deciduous forest) and culture.
 - Asia due to its prominence within the forest therapy research field.
 - Time period:
 - 2019-2024
 - Keywords:
 - forest therapy; forest bathing; Shinrin-yoku; environment
- A small number of papers specifically considered the environment in which the programme was being conducted, including:
 - Four conceptual papers, which provided theoretical and/or empirically informed frameworks for characterising the nature component [44,90-92].
 - Six empirical papers about forest therapy/forest bathing/Shinrin-yoku, which reported details about the environmental setting [41, 93-97].
 - One systematic review/meta-analysis paper, which evaluates the relationship between the forest structure and therapeutic effect [98].
- We developed an integrated framework (drawn largely from the four conceptual papers) to assess the six empirical papers in terms of environmental characteristics.
- Our integrated framework considers four scales - landscape, site, forest, trail - which are illustrated in Figure 8, and defined as follows:
 - *Landscape*
 - The broadest category, encompassing features that influence site, forest, and trail levels.

Figure 7: Nature in the context of NBIs

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Table 5: Description of environment in identified empirical forest therapy studies

Region	Landscape	Site	Forest	Trail	Comments
Asia (3 papers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 mention landforms and forest cover % • 1 mentions population and transportation & tourism resources • 1 mentions aesthetics (natural phenomena) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 mention land ownership and designation being national • 2 mention altitude • 3 mention the specific species 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 detail forest structure characteristics focusing on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Canopy characteristics - Average diameter at breast height (dbh) - Average height - Age. • 1 mentions forest composition (stand density) and area 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 mentions route altitude and facilitating sensory stimulus (proximity to site and forest features that stimulate the senses) • 1 mentions environmental factor(s) of the route (wind) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trail characteristics was the least reported
Europe (3 papers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 mentions proximity to urban areas 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 mentions land ownership • 1 mentions altitude and water features • 2 mention specific species 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 mentions the forest composition species 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 mention accessibility measures taken at the trail 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All 4 characteristics had very little that could be extracted
USA/ Canada (0 papers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • n/a 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • n/a 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • n/a 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • n/a 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No empirical studies reporting characteristics of environment

3. Forest therapy as a health and wellbeing intervention in Scotland

- This section ties together the what (forest therapy – Section 2) and the so-what (public health challenges and interventions – Section 1) through the notions of green and social prescribing.
- There is already evidence that public policy in Scotland is aligned with the principles of social prescribing and that nature is good for you.
- Programmes exist that health care professionals can signpost people to that can support health and wellbeing challenges; examples of green social prescribing exist, but it is less well-established in Scotland than its parent concept, social prescribing.
- We propose forest therapy as an activity that may complement social and healthcare practitioners’ green social prescribing toolkit.
- We have undertaken a feasibility and acceptability study to deliver data to evidence that proposal as a means to evaluate and analyse programmes’ suitability for prescription as forest therapy interventions – in the final section we outline our research approach and indicate next steps.

3.1 Green and social prescribing

- The concept of prescribing health and wellbeing interventions founded in nature (such as forest therapy) has received some attention in the media [99,100], including articles advocating for the science and benefits of forest bathing to underpin green prescribing by NHS doctors.
- This section considers the concepts and structures that forest therapy would integrate into should it be adopted as a health and wellbeing intervention promoted in clinical settings and through green health infrastructure (Section 1.3).

3.1.1 Social prescribing

- In Scotland, the term ‘social prescribing’ is “*used to describe a variety of approaches by which individuals are linked to resources and services within local communities with the aim of improving mental and physical health and wellbeing*” and is also described as “*an important approach to self-management of mental health*” [101] (p. 35).
- Social prescribing is also sometimes known as ‘community referral’ [102-104].
- Research conducted to establish internationally accepted conceptual and operational definitions of social prescribing has been reported in the British Medical Journal and a framework based on common understanding has been developed [105].
- The ‘CUSP’ (Common Understanding of Social Prescribing) Framework [105] identifies key actors and describes the process linking people with health-related social needs to services that support delivery of those needs.
- Social prescribing schemes include a range of services giving practical information and advice, and can include community activities, physical activities, and befriending and enabling services; they are commonly provided by organisations within the voluntary and community sectors [106].

- Networks, organisations, charities, and health boards across Scotland are involved in operationalising and developing social prescribing, including: the Scottish Social Prescribing Network (SSPN), which was established in 2020 as a result of the Covid-19 pandemic [107]; Change Mental Health, who are a delivery partner working with 29 GP practices across Highland [104]; and Volunteer Scotland, who published a report advocating for the significance of volunteers and community sector organisation in the delivery of social prescribing, and also the importance of volunteering as an intervention measure in itself [108].
- In an inventory of resources provided for staff working in primary care services, 14 social prescribing tools are identified and information provided, including Green Health Partnerships alongside other examples such as ALISS (web-based resource mapping community assets), Health on the Shelf (health and wellbeing offerings in Scotland's public libraries), and Befriending Networks [101].

3.1.2 Green social prescribing

- Spending time in nature has been included in examples of social prescribing activities [102,109], forming a core type of referral known as 'green social prescribing' [110].
- Green social prescribing can include "*nature-based activities, such as gardening, care farming, open water swimming, or walking in nature, which may include formal therapy or a mindfulness component*" [110] (p. 421).
- As a category of social prescribing, green social prescribing includes group-based programmes (e.g. group walks in nature) and self-directed activities (e.g. spending time alone in nature).
- Studies discussing green social prescription practices have advocated for nature therapy as an opportunity to support improved mental health [109-112] and social connectedness [109] and have found that GPs' attitudes are positive towards the concept, believing them to be achievable within general practice [113].
- A recent study on green social prescribing for DEFRA reported statistically significant improvements across a range of wellbeing measures as well as return on investment [114].
- Research on the related concept of green exercise (which combines *physical* activity in a natural environment) suggests greater physical and mental health benefits than physical activity or nature contact alone [115].
- A recent rapid evidence review on how the natural environment can support health and wellbeing through social prescribing includes recommendations relating to the development of referral pathways, attention to health inequalities and access restrictions, need for evaluation tools, and suggestion for integrating programmes with an indoor and outdoor component [116].
- Findings from a pragmatic controlled trial comparing forest bathing with an established wellbeing intervention (Compassionate Mind Training) revealed equivalence between the two approaches in terms of heart rate variability (HRV) and wellbeing measures, providing support for forest therapy in the context of social prescribing [45].

3.1.3 Green social prescribing in Scotland

- A 2010 report on green prescription schemes by NHS Health Scotland and SNH^g described the results of a survey, whereby 94 schemes were identified that include aspects of physical activity in outdoor settings with strong natural environment components (e.g. greenspaces, paths, parks, nature reserves, and countryside) and which had some type of referral mechanism from health care practitioners [117].
- More recently, online infrastructure developed by Scotland's four pilot Green Health Partnerships (Section 1.3.2) is signposted as a resource to primary care staff [101], and potential has been identified for referral pathways connecting interventions with social prescribing [66].
- Dundee Green Health Partnership launched Scotland's first Green Health Prescription pathway in 2019, linking patients with more than 60 weekly green health activities across the city through healthcare professionals and community service prescription, and providing opportunities for self-referral [118,119].
- Green referral pathways in the Highland and North Ayrshire GHP areas are also in early stages of implementation [60].
- Scotland's Community Link Workers currently offer an alternative route, connecting patients and GPs with green health interventions.
- Darach Social Croft represents an example where connections between local health care professionals and the provider are established, and over time a green health programme has been developed to promote mental wellbeing and tackle social isolation [120, 121].
- Collaboration between the RSPB and healthcare providers across Scotland represents another example of how green social prescribing is being implemented, for example: [Here is your nature prescription](#) [122].

3.1.4 Forest therapy as an intervention suitable for green social prescribing

- Throughout this report, we provide support for our exploration of forest therapy as suitable for green social prescribing, including:
 - Forest therapy has been shown to have significant mental health and wellbeing benefits in international studies (Section 1.2.2) – including for key public health challenges currently prioritised by the Scottish Government (Section 1.1).
 - Scotland's *Our Natural Health Service* illustrates an acknowledgement of the value of nature-based interventions for health and wellbeing in the context of Scottish policy (Section 1.3).
 - Mechanisms and structures are developing to support green social prescribing as a practice in Scotland (Section 3.1.3).
 - Forest therapy has already been identified in the literature, media, and in practice as an activity with potential for green social prescribing.
 - The benefits of forest therapy as an intervention in the context of green social prescribing predominately related to mental health and wellbeing objectives, but forest therapy may also represent an accessible form of green exercise for those

^g Scottish Natural Heritage – now NatureScot

- with physical health limitations, due to the short distances and slow pace involved (Section 2.2.2).
- Forest therapy has potential to be integrated into Scotland’s green health offering (Section 1.3.2) as a preventative and responsive intervention for mental health and wellbeing.
 - Forest therapy is well designed to be integrated to clinical care on the basis that organisations and standards exist that support critical understanding of what it has to offer and ensuring consistency and legitimacy in the manner of implementation (Section 2.2.1)
 - There are an increasing number of forest therapy practitioners in Scotland, including fifteen guides trained in association with Scottish Forestry and independent guides located in different parts of the country (e.g. Table 4), and mechanisms exist for additional providers to become qualified (see Table 3).
- The next section outlines new research undertaken in Scotland focusing on how one might monitor and evaluate forest therapy as a nature-based intervention.

3.2 Forest therapy as an intervention for women 40 years and older

- This section describes new research investigating forest therapy as a nature-based activity for women 40 years and older in Scotland.
- Our study explores the feasibility and acceptability of recruitment and study procedures, outcome measures, and the impacts of conducting research alongside forest therapy as a nature-based health and wellbeing intervention. It also explores whether this type of experience might shift nature relationships and values.
- Here we provide a brief description of the research approach taken; findings will be presented in subsequent reports.

3.2.1 Study aims, hypothesis, and research questions

- Our aim is to assess the feasibility of conducting research on and acceptability of forest therapy as a nature-based intervention for mental health and wellbeing, and for changes in relationship with and values toward nature.
- We have identified a demographic for whom forest therapy might generate benefits – women 40 years and older, a group within the population who may encounter challenges associated with the menopausal transition.
- Key hypotheses underpinning our approach are that: 1) a 120-minute forest therapy experience could provide a nature dose supportive of change in stress and emotions, overall health and wellbeing, and values in relation to nature; and 2) changes will become continuously evident over a 1-2 week-period.

- Through investigating *the potential of forest therapy as a programmatic nature-based intervention mechanism*, our study explores the following questions in the 2022-2027 Scottish Government Strategic Research Programme:
 1. To what extent could forest therapy support use of the outdoors in the context of green social prescribing for health and wellbeing?^h
 2. What is the potential for forest therapy to transform values toward nature?ⁱ

3.2.2 Research design and data collected

- This is a small-scale feasibility and acceptability study based on a forest therapy intervention walk. Data were collected using a variety of qualitative and quantitative data before, during and after, including questionnaires, an art-based activity, and interviews (see Figure 9).
- We adopted a case study approach, recruiting women 40 years and older in the Aberdeen, Scotland area to participate in a protocolised forest therapy walk with an established forest therapy guide in a locally available woodland.
- Three forest therapy walks were conducted in September/October 2024 in woodlands on the outskirts of Aberdeen, also allowing us to reflect on the significance of the location and environment of forest therapy experiences (see Section 2.2.4) and engaging with debates that seek to link nature and accessibility to health and wellbeing of urban communities [53,109,123].

Figure 9: Study design and implementation

- Figure 9 illustrates the key stages of data collection and details associated with recruitment, enrolment, and completion:
 - Sixty enquiries were received in response to online and poster advertisements across Aberdeen. Following study eligibility screening interviews and questions

^h Addressing *Reciprocal Care for Nature and Wellbeing (JHI-C6-1)* RQ1: What mechanisms can support use of the outdoors with a focus on green prescribing for mental and physical health and wellbeing?

ⁱ Addressing *People and Nature (JHI-D4-1)* RQ10: The potential for interventions to transform biodiversity/nature values?

regarding availability to participate, 28 women were enrolled to participate in the study. Twenty-four individuals joined across the three walks and completed the study; drop-outs occurred due to change in circumstances (e.g. illness, childcare arrangements).

- The baseline survey, conducted prior to the walk date, asked questions about the participant's current health, menopause experiences, feelings and emotions, self-care, and demographic profile.
- The pre-walk survey, completed just prior to going out on the guided forest therapy walk, asked questions relating to the participant's day, current feelings and emotions, and relationship with the natural environment.
- The post-walk survey, completed after the walk, asked many of the same questions as the pre-walk survey to gauge differences following the forest therapy experience.
- In addition to the post-walk questionnaire, participants completed an art activity just after the walk, providing a different medium to explore the forest therapy walk experience.
- For six days following the walk, participants completed a brief survey asking about their time spent in nature and how they are feeling.
- At one week and two weeks after the guided forest therapy walk, participants completed a survey exploring ongoing effects and changes following the walk experience. Questions asked about time spent in nature, thoughts, feelings and emotions, relationship to nature, health/wellbeing questions, self-care, meaningful life changes, and any comments on survey completion.
- The final questionnaire, conducted 3 weeks after participation in the forest therapy walk, served as a feasibility and acceptability survey investigating participants' experiences in the study and being part of the project.
- Final interviews were conducted with half of the study population. Questions explored participants' expectations and motivations for taking part in the study, feelings about the forest therapy experience and changes in behaviour since participating, an interactive nature values activity, feedback on the study experience, and opportunity to share any final thoughts.
- Recruitment through to data collection was completed between August and December 2024.

3.2.3 Next steps

- Qualitative and quantitative data analyses will inform reports in Year 4 (2025/26) and Year 5 (2026/27) of the Scottish Government RESAS Strategic Research Programme (2022-2027).
- Reports will focus on:
 - Results from investigating the feasibility and acceptability of recruitment and data collection procedures, measures used to assess the experience of taking part in a forest therapy walk, and the acceptability to participants and the guide of integrating evaluative research into forest therapy as a mechanism to support mental health and wellbeing for this demographic.

- Results from investigation of participants' relationship with and values toward nature, drawing out the potential for forest therapy to support shifts in an individual's relationship to nature and biodiversity.
- Findings can provide preliminary evidence to support integration of forest therapy as an option for green social prescribing.
- Results could inform development of further research – pilot study, large-scale (e.g. randomised) – with sufficient numbers of participants to measure effects and significance.

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